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REPEATED IMPACT RESPONSES OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS

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Introduction

Repeated impact loadings in marine structures

- Ship and offshore structures are frequently subjected to repeated impact loadings such as dropped objects, ice floes as well as slamming loads, resulting in the dynamic deformation and accumulation damage of marine structures.
- Improve impact resistance and energy absorption capacities of marine structures.

Aluminium honeycomb sandwich panels

- Honeycomb sandwich panels can possess excellent energy absorption capabilities and have been widely used in the structural impact protection.

Aluminium honeycomb harden composition

Numerical calculation method

- Dynamic behaviour of sandwich panel with honeycomb core under repeated impact loadings is investigated by using the commercial software ABAQUS Explicit.
- The dimension of the square sandwich panel is **180 mm×180 mm**.
- Isotropic elastoplastic material model** is used for honeycomb sandwich panel.
- Stress-strain curves** were obtained through the standard uniaxial tension tests.
- Fixed boundary condition** is defined in the top and bottom face sheet edges.

Drop weight repeated impact test

- Repeated impact tests were conducted by using **INSTRON Drop Tower 9350**.
- Total impact mass** can be changed from 2.5 kg to 70 kg.
- Maximum impact velocity** can be up to 24 m/s.
- Experimental results were obtained from the force transducer and analyzed by the data acquisition system (DAS 64K).
- Fixed boundary condition** was achieved by using the upper and lower clampers.

Numerical result and experimental validation

